

Synthesis, characterization, thermal stability and antimicrobial activities of transition metal complexes of 8-[2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-acetyl]amino-4-methyl-7-oxo-2-thia-6-azabicyclo[4.2.0]oct-4-ene-5-carboxylic acid

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Abstract : The complexes of 8-[2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-acetyl]amino-4-methyl-7-oxo-2-thia-6-azabicyclo[4.2.0]oct-4-ene-5-carboxylic acid (L) with Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{III} of composition [MLX₂] (M = Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{III}; X = Cl) were prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, UV-Visible, Mass, SEM and thermogravimetric studies. As elemental analysis suggests ML stoichiometry for all metals, conductivity data suggests that all the complexes are non-electrolyte in nature. Similarly, magnetic susceptibility, spectral and thermal studies suggest that all the complexes possess octahedral geometry. The synthesized metal complexes were screened for their antimicrobial activities against bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results were found to exhibit potent biological activity against both bacteria which increased in the forms of their metal complexes.

Keywords : Synthesis, characterization, metal complex, IR, UV-Vis, antimicrobial.

Introduction

Development of new methodologies is helpful in the synthesis of inorganic compounds as therapeutic agents. It is well known that the action of many drugs is dependent on the coordination with metal ions and the inhibition on the formation of metalloenzymes. Therefore, metal ions might play a vital role during the biological process^{1,2} of drug utilization in the body and also used in medicine for various biological properties. This activity of transition metals has started the development of metal-based drugs with promising pharmacological applications and may offer unique therapeutic opportunities. Metal complexes also offer a platform for the design of novel therapeutic compounds. The biological activity of many drugs has been shown to be enhanced on complexing with metal ions, promoting their use in pharmacology. Activity of cefadroxil compound can be increased by the formation of complex with different metal ions^{3,4}. Cefadroxil (CFDX) is a semi-synthetic first generation broad spectrum antibiotic that is active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. It is used for the treatment of urinary tract infection, pneumonia, skin and soft tissue infections and acute bronchitis. The structure

formula^{5,6} of cefadroxil is shown in Fig. 1. Not much has been reported about the antibacterial activity of these complexes. The metal complexes of CFDX show better antibacterial activity than the antibiotics themselves. Here, the spectral, structural, and antimicrobial properties of iron(III), nickel(II) and ruthenium(III) complexes of cefadroxil (CFDX) are reported with the spectral property and antimicrobial activity of the complexes⁷ compared to its corresponding ligand.

Fig. 1. The structure of CFDX.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. 8-[2-Amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-acetyl]amino-4-methyl-7-oxo-2-thia-6-azabicyclo[4.2.0]oct-4-ene-5-carboxylic acid (CFDX)

were obtained from Sigma Aldrich.

Physical measurements :

The analysis of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were performed in Elementar, Vario analyzer at CSMRI, Bhavnagar, Gujarat. IR spectra were recorded as KBr disc in the 400–4000 cm^{-1} region using a Bruker FT-IR spectrometer. Electronic spectra of the metal complexes in DMF were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer UV Win Lab spectrophotometer in the range 200–800 nm at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The mass spectra were carried out on the Waters Quadrupole Time of Flight (Q-TOF) Micromass (LC-MS) spectrometer at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. A simultaneous TG/DSC was recorded on Mettler Toledo Model at CSIR-AMPRI, Bhopal.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

In the preparation of the metal complexes, the metal ion salts and the ligand were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio using 80 : 20 ratio of ethanol-water mixture. Ethanolic solution of ligand (0.01 mol) with corresponding metal salts (0.01 mol) MX_2 (where $\text{M} = \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Pt}^{\text{II}}$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$) were mixed together, refluxing the reaction mixture for 2–3 h with constant stirring and left for evaporation at room temperature for 5 days and a coloured solid metal complexes were obtained. The product were filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried. Yield : 70–80%.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antibacterial activity of the free ligand and its Fe^{III} complex were tested against the Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*. The

tests were performed according to the disc diffusion method. The concentration of compound used for testing was 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in DMSO and used as control. The antibacterial activity of compound was evaluated by studying the growth inhibition against test microorganisms. The procedure was performed in separate plates for each microorganism.

Results and discussion

The analytical data for the ligand and complexes are given in Table 1 which agrees their proposed formulae. The complexes are coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF and DMSO. They are non-hygroscopic, highly stable under normal conditions and all of them decompose at higher temperature.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the complexes are compared with those of the free ligand in order to determine the coordination sites that may involve in chelation. The IR spectrum of the free ligand shows a sharp band at 3507 cm^{-1} is due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded phenolic νOH group. The absence of this band in the spectra of metal complexes indicates the breaking of hydrogen bond and coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal after deprotonation. The IR spectra of all the metal complexes exhibited a broad band at 3386–3198 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of water molecules of crystallization, while the band observed at approximately 840–712 cm^{-1} is assigned to coordinated water⁸ and OH groups. The presence of bands at 645–611 cm^{-1} (M-N) confirms the bonding of nitrogen and oxygen atoms of ligand groups

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of ligand and its complexes

Sr. No.	Empirical formula of ligand/complex	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Colour	m.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
					Found (Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	Metal
1.	CFDX	363.389	Off white	197	48.59 (52.88)	4.80 (4.72)	10.52 (10.89)	–
2.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{CFDX})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	455.22	Dark brown	362	41.83 (42.21)	2.89 (3.76)	8.01 (8.15)	11.25 (12.26)
3.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{CFDX})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	458.07	Green	270	40.34 (41.94)	3.23 (3.74)	9.05 (9.17)	11.25 (12.81)
4.	$[\text{Ru}(\text{CFDX})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	500.45	Dark brown	382	37.73 (38.39)	3.06 (3.42)	7.98 (8.39)	18.27 (20.19)

to the metal cation. The band observed at 1685 cm^{-1} has arrived from stretching vibrations of amide carbonyl group. This band shifted at 1669 , 1602 and 1603 cm^{-1} in Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} and Ru^{III} metal complexes.

Due to zwitterionic character of CFDX, the spectrum of free ligand shows bands of asymmetric $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and symmetric $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ vibrations of carboxylate group at 1562 and 1396 cm^{-1} , respectively. In spectra of Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} and Ru^{III} metal complexes this $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ band is shifted towards lower wave number⁹. Thus the IR spectral results provide strong evidences for the complexation of drugs with metal ions. The above discussion supports the proposed structure^{8,10} of synthesized metal complexes.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic absorption (UV-Vis) spectra of metal complexes were recorded in DMSO, in the range of $200\text{--}800\text{ nm}$. The magnetic moment data and the possible assignments of the complexes are also presented in the same table. These values are closer to those reported in some similar type of complexes. The UV spectrum for CFDX shows absorption bands¹¹ at 34843 cm^{-1} and at 32154 cm^{-1} . Two well resolved bands for unhydrolysed CFDX with absorption maxima at 46728 cm^{-1} and 37878 cm^{-1} attributed to $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{C}-$ and $-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{COO}-$ groups^{9,12} were observed. The obtained magnetic moment of both the Fe^{III} complex is 5.01 B.M. The electronic spectra of

Fe^{III} complex shows a weak intensity band between $18755\text{--}23540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which correspond to spin allowed transitions assigned to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ within the range of values corresponding to a high spin octahedral arrangement. The absorbance spectra of this complex have transitions confirming an octahedral arrangement¹³.

The magnetic moment of the CFDX- Ni^{II} complex has been found to be 3.34 B.M. which is within the range of values corresponding to distorted octahedral geometry. The absorbance spectra of CFDX- Ni^{II} complex are consistent with this assignment. The appearance of three bands at $13227\text{--}18870\text{ cm}^{-1}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $23825\text{--}33470\text{ cm}^{-1}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ are supportive and consistent with this assignment^{14,8}.

The magnetic moment of CFDX- Ru^{III} complex were found 1.90 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron in trivalent ruthenium in octahedral environment¹⁵ of electronic configuration ${}^1T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$. The spectrum shows the absorption band at $28571\text{--}27777\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These transitions are attributed to the $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(d\pi) \rightarrow \text{bpy}(\pi^*)$ metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) transitions, respectively (Fig. 2).

Mass spectra :

Mass spectra of the ligands and their metal chelates show molecular ion peaks, which are in good agreement with the calculated values. The mass spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S})-$

Fig. 2. CFDX- Ru^{III} .

(H₂O)₂] shows a molecular ion peak (m^{•+}) at m/z 475 and 518. The mass spectrum of all the complexes indicates that the complexes are monomeric¹⁶⁻¹⁸, confirming the metal to ligand ratio to be 1 : 1 in the complexes (Fig. 3).

A total weight loss of 51.16%, 55.53% and 50.66% have been observed with these three steps. The final residue appeared as 49.75%, 44.81%, 49.78% for Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{III}. These results are in a good agreement with the theoretical values^{19,20}. Thermal data of the complexes

Fig. 3. CFDX-Ni^{II}.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

In order to know the presence of water molecules and decomposition pattern of complexes, thermal analysis of all the complexes were carried out by the TG-DSC technique. The experimental results revealed that the degradation occurred in multiple stages, following a complex mechanism. In the present investigation, heating rates were suitably controlled at 10 °C min⁻¹ and mass loss followed upto 50–800 °C. The simultaneous TG-DSC curve of the CFDX-Fe^{III} is presented in Fig. 4. The TG curve follows the decrease in sample mass with increase in temperature.

The thermogram curves of the all CFDX complexes i.e. Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{III} shows that the decomposition takes place in three stages in the range of 272–800 °C. The first stage occurred with endothermic peak between temperature ranges of 59–198 °C. This stage is due to the loss of water molecules with a continuous weight loss⁹. The second and third decomposition stages occurred in two steps in the range from 235–450 °C and 450–600 °C.

are listed in Table 2.

Biological activity :

In antibacterial study, the inhibition effects of the synthesize compounds on the growth of various microorganism are listed in Table 3. The results for antibacterial study are interpreted by measuring the zones of inhibition of growth of the bacterial culture. The results show that ligand CFDX and Fe^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes exhibit bacteriostatic behavior towards both the bacterial strain using disc diffusion method. The Fe^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes were found showing good activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. In general, the results reveal that the activity of the ligand was found to be enhanced on complexation with metal ions. Thus, it is revealed that, the Ru^{III} complex of CFDX is able to inhibit almost all the studied Gram-positive and Gram-negative organism at the higher dose level with an inhibition zone ranging between 13–29 mm. It has been observed that the metal complexes show enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to the free ligand.

Fig. 4. CFDX-Fe^{III}.

Table 2. Thermo analytical data of the complexes

Sr. No.	Metal complexes	Total weight for TGA (mg)	Temperature range of water loss (°C)	TG weight loss (%)		Decomposition temperature (°C)	Weight of residue (%)
				Found	Calcd.		
1.	CFDX	16.55	-	85.54	83.23	209-444	15.08
2.	[Fe(CFDX)(H ₂ O) ₂]	12.23	67-133	51.16	50.15	272-622	49.75
3.	[Ni(CFDX)(H ₂ O) ₂]	22.78	100-154	55.53	55.00	403-786	44.81
4.	[Ru(CFDX)(H ₂ O) ₂]	21.80	115-155	50.66	50.10	390-800	49.78

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of ligand and complexes (Measurement of zones)

Sr. No.	Bacterial strains	Zone of inhibition (Diameter in mm)							
		Ctrl.	Std.	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S(CFDX) (µg/ml)			[Ru(C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S)Cl ₂] (µg/ml)		
				150	300	600	150	300	600
1.	<i>E. coli</i>	-	22	-	8	14	-	13	28
2.	<i>S. aureus</i>	-	30	-	10	16	-	15	29

Conclusion

Based on the physicochemical and spectral data discussed above, octahedral geometry for Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{III} complexes have been proposed. Thermal study revealed that complexes are thermally stable, biologically active and shows enhanced antimicrobial activities compared to the free ligand.

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